

THE CONCEPT OF LINGUISTIC VIEW OF THE WORLD AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN LINGUACULTUROLOGY

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Abstract: Language shapes our perception of the world and influences cultural values. The anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics has led to the concept of the linguistic picture of the world, studied in cognitive linguistics and linguocultural science. This article explores its development, including ideographic dictionaries and lexical-semantic fields. Scholars attribute its origin to W. Hertz or L. Wittgenstein. It connects to V. Humboldt's views on language as a dynamic system with interconnected elements and mutual contradictions. E. Sapir and B. L. Whorf's theory highlights how language affects cultural behaviors. The article examines cognitive processes underlying the linguistic world picture, emphasizing imagination and logical processing.

Keywords: Language, perception, cultural values, anthropocentric paradigm, linguistics, cognitive linguistics, linguistic picture of the world, ideographic dictionaries, lexical-semantic fields, W. Hertz, L. Wittgenstein, W. Humboldt, dialectical method, interconnectedness, mutual contradictions, subjective description

Language is not just a means of communication, but it shapes our perception of the world and affects our cultural values, and at the same time, it provides information about the worldview, lifestyle, worldview, and customs of the people of that nation. The emergence of the modern trend in linguistics, that is, the emergence of the antopocentric paradigm, is studied in connection with linguistics and various sciences, in particular, psychology, ethnography, cultural science, sociology, etc., and the main central point of linguistics is considered to be a person. As a result, the concept of the linguistic picture of the world appeared and serves as the main object of study of cognitive linguistics and linguocultural science.

In linguistics, the emergence of the concept of the linguistic world picture, the practice of creating ideographic dictionaries and the structure and content of the lexical-semantic fields related to this, the study of the relationship between them, the emergence of the antopocentric direction, the study of language required the use of new methods.¹

Some scholars claim that the term linguistic picture of the world was first introduced by doctors, that is, W. Hertz, while another group of scholars believe that this concept was first introduced in L. Wittgenstein's "Logical and Philosophical Trilogy".²

According to A. Gabbasova and G. Fatkullina, the concept of the linguistic picture of the world is related to the views of V. Humboldt, who used the dialectical method in language analysis. This method implies that the world should be viewed as an ever-changing system, according

¹ Карданова К.С. Языковая картина мира: мифы и реальность [Текст] / К. С. Карданова // Русский язык в школе. – 2010. – № 9. – С. 61-65

² Mirjalilova M.J Linguistic world picture and its representation through phraseological units in the aspect of linguoculturology. Academic research in educational sciences, – 2021. – 94 b

to which everything is interconnected and at the same time forms a whole based on mutual contradictions. He viewed language as a system in which all elements are interconnected and can move from one state to another. For example, if we take the concept of happiness, one group of people considers happiness to be material well-being, while the other group understands that happiness is spiritual satisfaction. Both groups try to provide a general analysis of the concept of "happiness" and present conflicting arguments to support their point of view. As a result, it is possible to obtain a more accurate formulation of the concept of "happiness" that combines different points of view. So, the concept of happiness creates a different image in the minds of people, the subjective description of the objective existence reveals the meaning and content of the concept of the linguistic world picture of the world. In the minds of people, one sign creates different images depending on the culture, regional location, and lifestyle of the speakers of that language.

According to the theory of Linguist E. Sefir and his follower S. Whorf, the difference in the norms of thinking determines the difference in the norms of behavior in cultural and historical interpretation. Comparing the Hopi language with the "central European standard", S. Whorf tries to prove that the main categories of substance, space, and time can be interpreted differently depending on the structure of language attributes: "The concepts of "time" and "matter" are not the same for all people, they depending on the nature of the language or the languages developed by using them"³

The concept discussed above regarding the linguistic world picture is a crucial area of study within cognitive linguistics and linguocultural studies. It revolves around the understanding that language units shaping the imaginations and conceptsphere of language users differ when analyzing a specific concept. The questions of how a concept emerges and how it is expressed in words are explored. Within our minds, an object in motion is distinguished by its unique characteristics, and through generalization, it is grouped together with similar entities to form a general image. This image is then logically processed, becoming a concept, and prior to taking a linguistic form, it manifests as an imaginary model within the human mind. Linguist Sh. Safarov further divides this process into internal (inner) and external (outer) types, representing the movement of a concept from human imagination to its reflection in language.⁴ Before any concept is verbalized, it exists as a representation in the human mind and takes various forms in the speech of individuals.

In summary, the concept of linguistic world picture plays a significant role in linguistics, influencing how language shapes our perception of the world, and it is closely tied to the formation of our knowledge processes. This area is extensively researched in contemporary linguistics, and the connection between language and human beings continues to captivate the attention of scientists.

³ Whorf B. L. Relationships of norms of behavior and thinking to language [Text] / B. L. Whorf // History of linguistics of the 19th – 20th centuries in essays and extracts: in 2 parts. Part II. – M.: Education, 1965. – P. 255-281

⁴ M.Kistner M. Linguistic sign theories. – Seminar paper. – Germany: Green Verlag, 2005.

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